

FAILURE OF SINGLY CURVED SANDWICH PANELS SUBJECTED TO BLAST LOADING

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1 Introduction

The response of structures to blast loading is an area of growing concern as explosions due to accidents, terrorist attacks and war, gain a great deal of public attention because of the devastating damage and loss of life that follows. In parallel with increasing public concern, lightweight materials are increasingly used in structural applications because of their high specific strength and stiffness. Sandwich panels with lightweight deformable cores and stiff outer face sheets are a particularly attractive option when weight is a major design constraint.

This paper presents results from an investigation into the response of singly curved sandwich panels to blast loading. The sandwich panels have fibreglass epoxy laminate facesheets and PVC foam cores, all moulded in a single shot VARTM process. The aim of the experiments was to determine the influence of the curvature on the deformation and failure of the polymeric sandwich panels.

2 Previous work

Until the past decade, the majority of studies concerning the response of structures to blast loading focused on flat metallic plates, for example [1]. The response of curved panels to air-blast loading has not received the same level of attention. Shukla et al [2] presented strain and failure analysis data on the shock loading response of singly curved aluminium plates. Decreasing the radius of curvature changed the deformation mode and reduced the amount of yield line formation. Shen et al [3] examined the response of singly curved metallic sandwich panels to explosion loading. Similarly to [2], the curvature changed the deformation mode of the metallic sandwich panels, with an extended

flexural mode being observed when compared to equivalent flat sandwich panels. No work has been reported on the response of curved polymeric sandwich panels to air-blast loading.

2 Test Specimen Manufacture

2.1 Materials

Flat and singly curved sandwich panels were constructed using layers of 400g/m² plain weave E-glass fibre fabric, Prime 20 epoxy resin and an 80kg/m³ density PVC foam core (Airex C70.75).

2.2 Manufacturing

Firstly the flat foam core sheets were thermoformed to the required curvature (500 or 1000mm radius) by placing it the relevant curved mould underneath an electric heating mat, all within a vacuum bag. The electric heating blankets heated the thermoplastic core to 90°C for 15 minutes to soften the core. The vacuum pump was then switched on, shaping the core, and left on to maintain sufficient pressure during the thermoforming process, which is a further 15 minutes at 90°C. The heating blankets are then turned off while the vacuum pressure is maintained until the core has cooled, fixing the curved shape. This thermoforming process is shown in the photograph in Figure 1.

Figure 2 shows the VARTM process used to manufacture panels. The reinforcement and core materials are laid up dry in the same curved mould used for thermoforming and placed under a vacuum bag. Peel ply was used to ensure a consistent surface finish and separate the part from the flow promotion medium "Green Flow" which was used to ensure that the resin flowed above and below the dry

materials, and wetted out the entire part. To be consistent with industrial composite / foam core sandwich panel construction, each core was “spiked”. This results in a regular pattern of small holes (approximately 2.5mm in diameter) through the core. The purpose of these holes is twofold, firstly to ensure that the resin flows freely between the two skins and secondly to provide shear stiffeners between the two facesheets.

The resin was mixed and allowed to infuse under vacuum through the dry preform to produce the final curved sandwich panel. The panels were cut into squares with a projected shape of 400 x 400mm squares and post-cured at 50°C for 16 hours in an oven to ensure optimum mechanical properties. Replacing the curved mould with a flat mould allowed flat panels to be made in a similar way with no thermoforming of the core required. The standard construction consisted of 6 layers of the 400g/m² plain weave E-glass on either side of a nominally 15mm thick Airex C70:75 foam core. This resulted in a panel with approximately 1.8mm thick skins on either side of the PVC core.

3 Testing

3.1 Mechanical Testing

The material properties of the panels are determined by quasi-static compression and bend tests. The compressive stress of the foam was found to be 1.37 MPa, which corresponded well to the manufacturer’s supplied value of 1.3MPa.[4] Three point flexure testing was performed on beams cut from the flat sandwich panels in order to ensure consistency in the manufacturing process. The specimens were cut alongside the specimens for blast testing. ASTM International standards D7250/D7250M-06, and C393/C393M-06 [5,6] was used to calculate the face-sheet and core mechanical properties of the sandwich panels. The results were reasonably consistent, with reasonably low variances in quasi-static strength and can be seen in table 1.

3.2 Blast Testing

Both sets of panels were clamped between two steel frames, leaving a square projected area with a side length 300 mm exposed to the blast loading. The frames were mounted to a ballistic pendulum which was used to provide a measurement of the impulse

imparted to the panel. Photographs of the experimental arrangement are shown in Figures 3 and 4. The blast loading was generated by detonating 38mm diameter discs of PE4 plastic explosive at a stand-off distance of 100mm. Five panels of each configuration were tested using different masses of PE4 to vary the impulse.

A post mortem analysis was carried out on the flat and curved configurations. The modes of failure seen in the face-sheet can be seen in figure 5 and were delamination, matrix failure, fibre fracture and facesheet rupture. The delamination failure region was identified by a white visible region seen in photographs. Matrix failure is defined as a region where resin is missing from the composite but the fibre weave is still nominally intact. Fibre fracture is the appearance of the broken fibre material. Increasing fibre fracture occurs deeper through the thickness of the laminate making up the facesheet with the limiting condition being fibre fracture completely through the thickness. This defines rupture of the facesheet. The failure modes described here in the flat panels were also seen in the curved panels.

Figure 6 shows the failure modes of the core material, including core compression, core shear, core penetration and core fragmentation. Core compression is the permanent compression of the core material. Core shear is the cracking/splitting of the core material. Core fragmentation is the breaking apart of the core material. Core penetration is defined as the complete break away through the thickness of the core material.

Interface failure modes can also be seen in figure 6. This damage occurs by the debonding of the front and back face-sheets from the core material. Debonding was measured by inspecting a cross section cut through the midpoint of the panel. These cross-sections were cut parallel to the axis of curvature in the curved panels.

3.3 Results

Table 2 shows the measured values of delaminated area and interface debonded length (of the sectioned panels) against the charge mass and impulse. Figures 7 and 8 are graphs of the facesheet delamination versus impulse. In all cases, an increase in impulse

results in an increase in delamination damage on the front and back facesheets. In figure 7 the graph of the delamination for the front facesheet does not show any clear difference in the amount of delamination damage between the flat and curved panels, whereas the back facesheet graph (figure 8) suggests that the curved panels have less delamination damage than the flat panel as the applied impulse is increased. The tighter radius panel appears to perform best which is to be expected as the shape may deflect some of the applied blast wave. The close proximity to the blast of the front facesheet may explain why the delamination is similar in all cases.

Table 3 shows the increasing damage as the charge mass and hence impulse applied to the sandwich panels was increased. While it is possible to suggest a failure progression model, there are a number of failure mechanisms which are interlinked and cannot be easily separated. What is noted clearly is that even at low impulses, there was delamination damage visible on the front facesheet and debonding occurred between both the front and back facesheets and the core. This is expected as there is also corresponding core damage (compression and shear cracking of the core) from these low impulses as well.

For both the front and back facesheets, the damage followed a similar progression, with delamination, followed by matrix failure and fibre fracture and then rupture of the facesheet. Increasing the curvature of the panels appears to delay the onset of this damage on the back facesheet. What is not understood yet is why the cracking of the facesheets at the clamp edge only occurred on the 1000mm radius panel. This may be caused by a slight mismatch in the curvature between the sandwich panel and the clamp frame supporting the panel during the blast tests.

The core damage also followed a consistent trend. Core compression and shear cracking, were followed by penetration and fragmentation. In both the curved and flat panels, the penetration and fragmentation started at around 30Ns impulse and occurred at higher impulses than the front facesheet rupture.

From a blast performance perspective, the containment of the blast is of paramount importance. Hence back facesheet rupture is of particular interest here. For the flat panel, this occurs between an impulse of 35.1Ns and 37.7Ns. The 500mm radius panel performed better than the 1000mm radius panel with rupture occurring between 32.9Ns and 36.0Ns, but this is worse than the flat panel. The 1000mm radius panel is the worst performing of the panels with back facesheet rupture occurring at an impulse between 27.3Ns and 28.5Ns. The reasons for the flat panel outperforming the curved panels is unclear, however it should be noted that comparing these values to the charge mass rather than impulse, the effect of the deflection of the blast wave by the curved geometry is more apparent. The flat panel and the 1000mm radius panel are both able to survive a 17.5g PE4 charge, while the 500mm radius panel is able to withstand 22.5g of PE4.

4 Conclusions

Flat, 500mm radius and 100mm radius sandwich panels were manufactured with glass-fibre / epoxy facesheets on a PVC foam core. The material properties were characterized using quasi-static flexural and compression tests. Specimens with a projected 300mm square area were exposed to air-blasts of increasing charge mass on a ballistic pendulum. The resulting damage was analysed qualitatively and quantitatively. It appears that the geometry of the curved panels, especially at tighter radii, does deflect some of the blast wave away from the panel, and the panels are able to withstand higher charge masses at the 100mm standoff distance.

References

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Fig. 1. Photograph of the thermoforming process being performed on the 1000mm radius mould

Fig. 2. Schematic of VARTM process used.

Bend test data for sandwich panel flat plates				
Sandwich panels	P_{max} (N)	Displacement (mm)	σ_{face}^y (MPa)	σ_{core}^y (MPa)
Mean	1401	6.79	62.04	0.86
Std dev.	55	0.3	3.38	0.04

Table 1. Bend test data for sandwich panel flat plates

Fig. 3. Photograph of the ballistic pendulum setup used for blast tests

Fig. 4. Photograph showing the method of placing the explosive at the stand-off distance of 100mm

Fig. 5. Failure visible on a flat sandwich panel subjected to 15g charge of PE4

Fig. 6. Photograph showing examples of failure modes visible in the cross section, including core and interface damage.

Blast test results of the sandwich panels, showing delaminated and debonded lengths.						
Panel category	Charge mass (g)	Impulse (Ns)	Delaminated Area (%)		Debonded Length (mm)	
			Front	Back	Front	Back
Flat Sandwich Panel	10.0	17.4	6.2	0.7	72.4	0
	15.0	26.0	7.1	14.3	120.8	35.9
	17.5	35.1	9.0	28.4	112.8	54.4
	20.0	37.7	12.7	28.7	-	-
1000mm Radius Sandwich Panel	10.0	15.6	3.3	0	112.5	0
	12.5	18.7	5.0	5.9	111.7	21.2
	13.5	21.6	5.7	6.7	124	22.6
	15.0	24.5	4.3	1.7	136.1	31.1
	17.5	27.3	7.3	11.9	99.2	54.1
	18.5	28.5	8.2	6.0	-	-
	20.0	30.5	8.7	13.7	-	-
22.5	33.4	9.7	19.2	-	-	
500mm Radius Sandwich Panel	10.0	15.8	0.9	0	106.7	0
	12.5	19.4	4.4	0	107.5	0
	15.0	22.8	8.2	15.6	92.6	46.5
	17.5	26.1	8.4	3.8	106.4	28.3
	20.0	29.7	9.4	10.5	130.1	38.2
	22.5	32.9	11.9	9.2	159.1	50.2
	25.0	36.0	11.0	14.6	-	-
27.5	39.3	14.5	23.6	-	-	

Table 2. Blast test results of the sandwich panels, showing delaminated and debonded lengths.

Fig. 7 Graph of % delamination for the front face sheet against impulse

Fig. 8 Graph of % delamination for the back face sheet against impulse

Blast test results of the sandwich panels, showing identified failure modes of the panels						
Panel category	Charge mass (g)	Impulse (Ns)	Front facesheet damage	Back facesheet damage	Core damage	Facesheet-core interface damage
Flat Sandwich Panel	10.0	17.4	DL, MF, FF	DL	C, S	De _f , De _b
	15.0	26.0	DL, MF, FF, FR	DL	C, S	De _f , De _b
	17.5	35.1	DL, MF, FF, FR	DL, MF	C, S, P	De _f , De _b
	20.0	37.7	DL, MF, FF, FR	DL, FR	C, S, P, F	De _f , De _b
1000mm Radius Sandwich Panel	10.0	15.6	DL	None	C, S	De _f , De _b
	12.5	18.7	DL, MF, FF, FR	DL, C _o	C, S	De _f , De _b
	13.5	21.6	DL, MF, FF, FR, C _o	DL, C _o	C, S	De _f , De _b
	15.0	24.5	DL, MF, FF, FR, C _o	DL, C _o	C, S	De _f , De _b
	17.5	27.3	DL, MF, FF, FR, C _o	DL, C _o	C, S, P	De _f , De _b
	18.5	28.5	DL, MF, FF, FR	DL, FR, C _o	C, S, P, F	De _f , De _b
	20.0	30.5	DL, MF, FF, FR	DL, FR	C, S, P, F	De _f , De _b
22.5	33.4	DL, MF, FF, FR, C _o	DL, FR, C _o	C, S, P, F	De _f , De _b	
500mm Radius Sandwich Panel	10.0	15.8	DL, MF	None	C, S	De _f , De _b
	12.5	19.4	DL, MF, FF	None	C, S	De _f , De _b
	15.0	22.8	DL, MF, FF, FR	DL, MF	C, S	De _f , De _b
	17.5	26.1	DL, MF, FF, FR	DL	C, S	De _f , De _b
	20.0	29.7	DL, MF, FF, FR	DL	C, S, P	De _f , De _b
	22.5	32.9	DL, MF, FF, FR	DL, MF	C, S, P	De _f , De _b
	25.0	36.0	DL, MF, FF, FR	DL, MF, FF, FR	C, S, F	De _f , De _b
	27.5	39.3	DL, MF, FF, FR	DL, MF, FF, FR	C, S, F	De _f , De _b

DL – delamination
MF – matrix failure
FF – fibre fracture
FR – facesheet rupture
C_o – facesheet crack at the clamped region

C – compression;
S – shear;
P – penetration;
F - fragmentation

De_f – debonding between front facesheet and core
De_b - debonding between back facesheet and core

Table 3 Blast test results of the sandwich panels, showing identified failure modes of the panels